

PROBLEMS OF LEXICAL AND SEMANTIC INCOMPATIBILITY IN ORAL SPEECH TRANSLATION AND METHODS OF ELIMINATING THEM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistency that arise in the process of simultaneous translation, which is one of the most complex and responsible forms of oral speech translation, from a scientific, theoretical and practical perspective. The main problems encountered by the translator in the process of receiving, processing and transmitting speech in real time are terminological inconsistency, polysemy, phraseological units, cultural-realities (realia), and context-dependent semantic shifts. The article highlights the cognitive causes, psycholinguistic factors, and their impact on discourse, and proposes effective strategies for their elimination - advance preparation, contextual prediction, ensuring equivalence based on a functional approach, and using compensation and paraphrase methods. The results of the study serve to improve the quality of simultaneous translation, develop the professional competence of translators, and enrich the theory of translation studies.

Introduction.

The acceleration of globalization processes, the expansion of international political, economic, scientific and cultural ties have sharply increased the need for oral translation, in particular, simultaneous translation. Simultaneous translation is today one of the main communicative tools in international conferences, summits, diplomatic meetings, scientific forums and media activities. This type of translation requires a high level of language competence, quick thinking, psychological stability and the simultaneous implementation of complex cognitive processes from the translator.

The peculiarity of simultaneous translation is that the translator hears the speech in the source language, understands it semantically, and transmits it into the target language almost simultaneously. This real-time mode causes various problems in the translation process, especially lexical and semantic inconsistencies. Lexical inconsistencies are often associated with the lack of a suitable equivalent for terms, the polysemy of words, or their inconsistency

with the context, while semantic inconsistencies manifest themselves in the form of meaning shifts, pragmatic losses, and discursive imbalances.

These problems directly affect the quality and communicative effectiveness of simultaneous translation. An incorrectly selected lexical unit or a semantic solution that does not correspond to the context can lead to incorrect or incorrect perception of information by the listeners. Therefore, a deep scientific analysis of the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistency, identification of their causes and development of effective strategies for their elimination are one of the urgent issues of translation studies.

The purpose of this article is to identify the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistency that arise in the process of simultaneous translation, analyze them from a cognitive and psycholinguistic perspective, and justify optimal solutions and strategies that can be used in the practical translation process. The results of the study will serve to improve the professional training of simultaneous translators, improve the quality of translation, and develop the theory of oral translation.

Literature review on the topic:

Oral translation, and in particular the problems of simultaneous translation, have emerged as an independent object of research in translation studies since the second half of the 20th century. Initial scientific research was aimed at explaining the cognitive nature of simultaneous translation, explaining the complexity of this process by the simultaneous implementation of several psycholinguistic operations in the translator's mind.

The "Effort Model" developed by the famous scientist D. Gile provides a scientific explanation of the main causes of lexical and semantic inconsistencies that occur in the process of simultaneous translation. According to this model, the processes of listening and analysis, short-term memory, speech production, and coordination are carried out within the limited cognitive resources of the translator. As a result, the lack of resources leads to errors in lexical selection and semantic shifts.

The issue of lexical incompatibility has been studied mainly within the framework of equivalence theory. The concepts of formal and dynamic equivalence put forward by E. Nida emphasize that functional and communicative compatibility is more important than literal compatibility in simultaneous translation. In this regard, many researchers note that in simultaneous translation, it is preferable to choose not the absolute equivalent of lexical units, but the pragmatically correct, contextually appropriate variant.

The problems of semantic inconsistency are explained in close connection with discourse analysis and pragmatics. In the works of such scientists as T. van Dijk, M. Halliday, the concepts of contextual integrity of speech, layers of meaning and communicative intention play an important role. According to these approaches, semantic inconsistency in simultaneous translation occurs not only at the word level, but also within the entire speech discourse.

In recent years, the influence of cultural factors and realities on translation has been the focus of special attention. In particular, in the works of A. Schweizer and L. Barkhudarov, cultural-semantic inconsistencies are indicated as one of the main sources of loss of meaning in simultaneous translation. According to the authors, the translator acts not only as an interlingual, but also as an intercultural mediator. The problems of oral translation are also being gradually studied in local studies. In the works of Uzbek translation scholars, the issues of terminological compatibility, national mentality and speech etiquette in simultaneous

translation are of great importance. However, an analysis of the existing literature shows that the study of the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistencies in a complex, that is, cognitive, psycholinguistic and practical approaches has not yet been sufficiently carried out.

Therefore, this study, summarizing existing scientific views, aims to provide a deeper analysis of the mechanisms of origin of lexical and semantic inconsistencies in simultaneous translation and to develop practical strategies for their elimination.

Research methods:

This study aims to comprehensively study the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistency that arise in the process of simultaneous translation, using a number of theoretical and empirical research methods. The research methodology was developed based on the achievements of modern translation studies, psycholinguistics, and discourse analysis.

First of all, through the method of theoretical analysis, scientific sources on oral speech translation, simultaneous translation, and lexical and semantic equivalence were systematically studied. At this stage, the concepts of foreign and local scholars were comparatively analyzed, and the strengths and weaknesses of existing approaches were identified. This served to form the conceptual basis of the study.

The comparative-analytical method played an important role in the research process. With the help of this method, speech units in the source language and their translation variants in the target language were compared, and types of lexical and semantic inconsistencies were identified. The comparative analysis was carried out mainly on the basis of political speeches, scientific reports, and official conference speeches.

The method of discourse analysis was also used to study the communicative purpose, pragmatic orientation, and contextual integrity of speech. This method made it possible to determine that semantic shifts in simultaneous translation occur not only at the level of individual words or phrases, but also within the context of the entire speech content.

Within the framework of the psycholinguistic approach, factors related to the translator's cognitive load, short-term memory capacity, and attention allocation were analyzed. This approach was interpreted based on D. Jille's effort model, and it was scientifically substantiated that the lack of cognitive resources is one of the main causes of lexical and semantic inconsistencies.

In addition, observational and practical analysis methods were used. Audio and video materials on the practice of simultaneous translation were analyzed, strategies used by translators, errors and methods for their elimination were identified. The results obtained were summarized and scientific conclusions were drawn. This set of methods ensured the reliability and scientific validity of the research results and made it possible to comprehensively cover the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistency in simultaneous translation.

Results and discussion:

The results of the study showed that lexical and semantic inconsistencies in the process of simultaneous translation are systematic and recurrent. It was found that these inconsistencies are directly related not only to the level of language knowledge of the translator, but also to cognitive load, speech rate, complexity of the topic, and cultural factors.

The analysis showed that lexical inconsistencies mainly occur in the translation of terminological units, polysemantic words and phraseological expressions. In particular, in cases where there is no clear equivalent in the target language for specialized terms found in

scientific and political discourse, translators are forced to resort to generalization or paraphrasing methods. This in some cases leads to a decrease in the accuracy of information.

Lexical inconsistencies associated with polysemy often arise as a result of a lack of full understanding of the context. Due to time constraints in simultaneous translation, the translator does not always have the opportunity to deeply analyze the contextual meaning of the word. As a result, the wrong meaning may be selected, leading to a communicative error.

Semantic inconsistencies, on the other hand, are more evident at the discourse level. The results of the study showed that listeners misinterpret the content of the speech when the main idea, logical emphasis, or pragmatic purpose of the speech are not fully conveyed. In particular, semantic losses were observed in the translation of cultural realities, metaphors, and ironic expressions.

During the discussions, it was found that advance preparation is important in eliminating lexical and semantic inconsistencies. The translator's prior mastery of the subject-specific terminological base, the ability to predict the context of speech, and quick analysis skills significantly increase the quality of translation. It was also proven that an approach based on functional equivalence is more effective than word-for-word correspondence in simultaneous translation.

Practical analysis has shown that the strategies of compensation, generalization, reduction, and paraphrasing are the most commonly used by translators. These strategies, when used correctly and appropriately, allow to prevent semantic losses and maintain the communicative effectiveness of speech.

Overall, the results showed that lexical and semantic inconsistencies are an inevitable phenomenon in simultaneous translation, but they can be minimized through scientifically based strategies.

Conclusion and suggestions:

This study aimed to analyze the problems of lexical and semantic inconsistencies that arise in the process of simultaneous translation from a scientific, theoretical and practical perspective. The conducted analyses showed that inconsistencies in simultaneous translation are an integral part of the translation process and are closely related to the translator's cognitive load, time constraints, the complexity of the subject, and cultural factors.

In conclusion, it can be said that lexical inconsistencies are mainly manifested in the lack of terminological equivalents, the translation of polysemantic words and phraseological units. Semantic inconsistencies, on the other hand, arise as a result of a violation of the general content, pragmatic purpose and discursive integrity of speech. These situations can negatively affect the communicative effectiveness of simultaneous translation.

The results of the study showed that the approach based on functional equivalence, contextual analysis and compensation strategies are important in reducing lexical and semantic inconsistencies. The appropriate use of generalization, paraphrasing and abbreviating methods by the translator allows to minimize semantic losses.

The following practical suggestions can be recommended: - strengthening the formation of a terminological base and subject-oriented preparatory training in the process of training simultaneous interpreters; - introducing special training aimed at developing the psycholinguistic and cognitive skills of interpreters; - expanding training programs aimed at

improving intercultural communication competence; - conducting analytical training based on real speech materials in the practice of simultaneous interpretation.

The conclusions and suggestions presented in this article will help improve the theory and practice of simultaneous translation, increase the quality of translation, and serve as a methodological basis for future scientific research.

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